

Metadata element	Content
Dataset title	uc1b_nitrate_indicator_tier1_T31TCJ_20180602_20190602_NDVI_STACK_0.3_0.6.tif
Resource abstract	Nitrate leaching indicator due to crop rotation has been computed on agricultural parcels over an annual drainage period. The indicator and intermediary results (e.g. parcel identifier, mineralisation coefficient, NDVI values, etc.) are provided at pixel level.
Responsible organisation	ASP - IGN - INRAE
On-line resource	Zenodo
Topic Category	environment, farming
Keyword	Nitrate leaching indicator, agricultural parcels, crop sequence
Geographic bounding box	[(300000,4790220),(409800,4900020)]
Spatial resolution	10 m
Spatial representation type	raster
Coordinate reference system	EPSG:32631
Temporal coverage	From 02/06/2018 to 02/06/2019
Conditions for access and use	Licence: Creative Common - Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0) https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
Limitations on public access	None
Distribution format	GeoTIFF
Resource Language	eng
Lineage	<p>Source IACS data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - French RPG 2018 and 2019 - https://geoservices.ign.fr/documentation/donnees/vecteur/rpg - Seasonality information is present in the crop type classification <p>Temporal series of NDVI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sentinel-2 images used from 02/06/2018 to 03/02/2019 - Temporal NDVI series extracted from French national portal THEIA - MAJA mask used to detect cloudy areas and shadows <p>Theoretical calendar for intermediary cover</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Start date : 15/06/2018 - End date : 15/01/2019